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Sources: Everett, Dan L. & Barbara Kern, Wari'. The Pacaas Novos Language of Western Brazil, 1997

576 Wari' (dialect of the 'Oro Nao' clan ('ON))

I. Segmental Properties

Phonotactic patterns

- the coda position of CVC syllables is restricted to a number of Cs which may appear in it → only /n/ in word-medial position and only four other Cs additional to /n/ in word-finally position of the syllable
- plosives unreleased word-finally, e.g. Quep nain ['kE^p nãi] 'He touched it.', picot [pi'koʔ] 'armadillo species'
- no /kw/ or any of the affricates, fricatives, liquids or semivowels occur word-finally (but all plosives, nasals and sequences of P + N)
- all Cs word-initially, but the glottalized nasals (/m// and /n//, only word-finally) and /R/ (only in verbal inflectional clitics, but never isolated in an utterance → always utterance-medial)
- no word-initially C-clusters, but glottal plosive + C → [ʔC] as an allophone variant of the relevant C ([ʔC] fluctuates with [C] (/p/, /t/, /k/, /tS/, /S/, /m/, and /n/) word-initially, but glottal plosive always precedes word-initial semivowels (/w/ and /y/), even in polysyllabic words)
- no word-final C-clusters, but nasal + glottal plosive ([mʔ] and [nʔ] occur only word-finally)
- word-medial C-clusters rare in non-compounds; /n/ only C occurring as first element and /t/, /k/ and /tS/ as second element of a cluster (e.g. pantiri' (pan.ti.ri') [panti' Riʔ] 'our (incl.)son')
- all Vs word-finally, but none word-initially
- no sequences of syllabic Vs in monomorphemic words → V-sequences are realized as surface diphthongs
- diphthongs only in stressed syllables (only one example of an unstressed syllable)
- all diphthongs nasalized (only few diphthongs, which are not nasalized)
- Portuguese loan words are assimilated into 'ON phonology, e.g. /s/ and /z/ are realized as /S/ or one of its allophones, /f/ and /v/ are realized as [w], [h] or [hw], but there is no rule to predict exactly which of these forms will be adopted, /l/ is realized as [R], and all voiced plosives are realized as voiceless plosives

Phonological processes

- vowel harmony: does not apply across words, even when they have been compounded
 - incidence of identical vowels in successive syllables of the same word where /R/ is the medial C is very high (identical Vs preceding and following /R/; some words the result of partial reduplication, but the majority had not undergone any morphological processes), e.g. *xuruxut* 'walk (p)', *wereme* 'breathe'
 - *regressive assimilation* within words (not across morpheme boundaries) occurs when /e/ precedes a nasal or a plosive other than glottal plosive in a stressed syllable, by causing the /e/s in preceding contiguous syllables to take on its phonetic characteristics
 - V-harmony operates from right-to-left within the word; for harmony to spread, all Vs must be the same height
 - *progressive assimilation* occurs when /e/ causes /a/ and /i/ to change to /e/ and /o/ to /Y/; order of assimilation: the assimilation of /o/ to /Y/, which then causes the /e/s of the stem to change to /Y/ in regressive assimilation, e.g. were- (nose) + -con (3sm) → wurucun [wYRY'kYn] 'his nose'
 - *dissimilation* (vowel disharmony / dissonance) occurs when successive syllables of a word contain /i/ → the last /i/ causes the preceding /i/s in the word to be pronounced as [I], when pronounced slowly and clearly, all the /i/s are pronounced as [i]
- consonant harmony:
 - most assimilatory processes occur across word-internal morpheme boundaries
 - *regressive assimilation*: when -xi' nouns whose stems end with /ji/ inflect for third person masculine or feminine → the /k/ of the suffix causes the /y/ of the stem to change to /ts/, e.g. taraji- 'ear' + -con (3sm) → taraxicon [taRatSi'kon] 'his ear'
 - *progressive assimilation*: across morpheme boundaries between a N or nasalized diphthong and a voiceless stop; this assimilation is optional and is most common in normal speech; e.g. 'Om ca can ca. 'That is no grasshopper.' → [/om ga 'gan ga] [[/om ka 'kan ka] [[/om ga 'kan ga] [[/om ka 'kan ga]
 - no dissimilatory processes across morpheme boundaries
 - one process (just a fluctuation), where identical syllables in a word are reduced to a lengthened C
- coalescence is the most common assimilatory process in the language (V-harmony often accompanies coalescence)
 - V-coalescence takes a sequence of two Vs and returns a single V as output, according to the following principles: (1) if one of the two relevant Vs is marked [+back], the output V will be [+back]; (2) if the two Vs differ as to height, the output V will have the height of the highest V of the input

sequence; (3) if the Vs are identical (only case is /i/ + /i/), then a single, identical V is outputted

- asyllabification occurs when the INFL morpheme *co* occurs with 'aji' 'my older brother' in a *co*-kinship term: the prefix *co-* [ko] coalesces with the first syllable of [a'yi] to form [kwa]: *cwaji' ca* [kwa ' yi/ ka] 'his older brother' → this phenomenon also occurs in third person inflections of *-xi'* nouns ending with /o/ when /k/ is in the last syllable of the stem or first syllable of the suffix
- deletion processes:
 - word-final /// deletes before word-initial /h/
 - /// is deleted in kinship term formation, prior to asyllabification, e.g. *co-'aji-'iri* → *cwajiri* [k^wayi'Ri/] 'our (incl) older brother'
 - an oral V is nasalized preceding a tautosyllabic nasal C; in some idiolects word-final /n/ or /n// deletes across word boundaries
 - a process of truncation which occurs in the *-xi'* noun *tocoxi'* 'our (incl) eye' → when it inflects in the third person, *co* is deleted: *toco-* + *-con* = *tocon* 'his eye', not **tococon* (although this is correct for 'their (m) eyes') → not a result of the consonant reduction / harmony
- [l] fluctuates with [i] in unstressed syllables when the V in the following syllable(s) is [i]
- [Z] fluctuates with [y] before /i/, e.g. *maji* [ma'yi] or [ma'Zi] 'let's go!'
- [ö] rare phoneme, in some idiolects it seems to be evolving into [e] in open syllables and [Y] in closed syllables

Default syllable template

- 'ON has CV and CVC syllables
- minimal word construction is either CV or CVC; there are a few lexical morphemes in the form of suffixes that have a VC, VCVC or simply C construction → V-harmony, or the formation of a diphthong reduces the resulting combinations to a normal CVC pattern, e.g. *na* (3s:rp/p) + *-em* (2s) → *nem* [nlm] (3s:rp/p to 2s)

Super heavy syllables (SHS)

- none

II. Prosodic Properties

Stress

- within the sentence, the final syllable of major lexical categories are stressed
- primary sentence stress falls on the final syllable of the verb (or penultimate syllable if the final syllable is a stress-avoiding verb)
- secondary stress on the final syllable of other lexical categories
- tertiary (or even quaternary) stress on other morphemes like verbal inflectional clitics and inflectional forms of the preposition (but depending on the presence

of other constituents in the sentence), e.g. Mama' (go:p) nanain (3p:rp/p-3n) com (water) hwihima' (children). [ma¹ma/ na³näin²kom h^wiyi²ma/] 'The children went to the river.'

- emphasis on a constituent other than the verb will cause primary stress to be transferred to the emphasized constituent, e.g. [ma²ma/ na³näin²kom h^wiyi¹ma/] 'The *children* went to the water.'
- stress falls on the last syllable of the word, except when that syllable is a stress-avoiding member of a verbal compound, in which case stress will go on the syllable to its immediate left

Stress across a *morphologically complex word*

- in accordance with the rule of oxytonic primary stress in verbs, derived predicates in verbalized sentences also receive primary stress on the last syllable
- the stresses on the rightmost syllable of each individual word of the input will surface as secondary stresses in the output

Stress patterns with regard to compounding

- verb compounds of two or more verb stems also have two levels of stress: the rightmost member of the compound carries primary stress, while the preceding members carry secondary stress

Tone system

- no tone system
- no distinctive use of pitch
- only one basic intonation pattern: rising pitch through the verb, reaching high on the last syllable of the verb, and falling sharply on the next syllable (VIC or postverbal modifier that does not carry stress); it then holds through any optional arguments until the end of the sentence, or until a demonstrative or sentence-final particle, in which case it rises on the last syllable of the argument preceding the demonstrative or particle and falls sharply on the demonstrative or particle; in normal speech, the second high pitch is lower than the first high pitch
- higher pitch of intonation is transferred to the emphasized constituent when a constituent other than the verb is emphasized

III. Morpho-Syntax

Degree and types of fusion

- verbs most productive class → loan words enter Wari' as verbs; most remarkable fact about verbs is the almost complete absence of verbal inflectional processes alongside a rich set of derivational processes; verbs are uninflected by affixation, except for reduplication

- bound affixes: (1) set of possessive suffixes (mark number, person, and 3.person gender of the possessor on *-xi'* nouns), (2) a prefix, *co-* (marks the derivational process)
- zero-derivation:
 - words of one syntactic category are derived from other syntactic categories without affixation, i.e. a word, phrase or clause as input and a single word as output, with no affixation (e.g. English: *He is the head of...* vs. *He heads...*)
 - when the input is larger than a single grammatical word it may distinguished from the output prosodically since the output will receive a single primary stress on its rightmost syllable
 - the stresses on the rightmost syllable of each individual word of the input will surface as secondary stresses in the output
 - verbs may be built via zero-derivation from: sentences and nominals like emphatic pronouns or nouns
 - nouns may be derived from: subsentential constituents like INFL + verb (e.g. *ca tarama' nexi'* 'we men' (not 'our men') → first *tarama'* 'man' undergoes 0-derivation to form a verb 'to (be a) man' or 'to grow' and then, it and *ca* undergo 0-derivation to form a noun, to which is attached the NIC *nexi'* 'possessive-1pincl'); verb + VIC (excluding the INFL morpheme while including the VIC; no NIC can be added); few examples of nouns derived from clauses; derivation of *wa* 'infinitive' clauses; kinship terms (only examples of 0-derivation from clauses containing both INFL and VICs; they undergo phonological processes other 0-derived nouns fail to undergo; the processes not productive, since only kinship terms are so derived; e.g. *coweri'* 'our (incl) older sister' → *we* first verbalized via 0-derivation and then combined with *co* and *'iri'* to form a noun zero-derived from a clause (literal translation 'we older sister'); kinship terms form a tighter phonological unit than other nouns derived from *co* → certain phon. changes: asyllabification and glottal deletion; 1.p.pl. VICs also more intimate phonological connection to the derived kinship term than in nominalized sentences: (1) word-initial glottal on *'iri'* '1pincl' and *'urut* '1pexcl', as well as word-final glottals where applicable, are dropped; (2) vocalic harmony occurs between the root and suffix; and (3) primary stress is transferred from the basic form of the kinship term to the last syllable of the VIC); non-productive zero-derivation of nouns from verbs
- compounding:
 - highly productive derivational process in 'ON
 - nearly all multimorphemic verbs are derived via compounding (except for zero-derived phrases), with reduplication accounting for the rest → verbs never undergo affixation (aside from reduplication)
 → in 'ON verbal morphology almost exclusively derivational
 - compounding not a productive process for nouns

- nouns occur in verbs only by zero-derivation, often followed by compounding
- only clear cases of inflectional morphology are then -xi' nouns, the preposition, NICs and VICs and possibly the emphatic pronouns
- *///*-derivation: few cases of verbs derived from nominals (and one derived from a demonstrative) involve the addition of a glottal (or glottalized nasal) to the end of the noun to derive the verb (no other phonological changes observed)
- derivation from VICs: there are two kinship terms and one verb which might have been derived from VICs, although this is still speculative

Infixation, circumfixation or simulfixation, Reduplication

- very productive, ranges from monosyllabic and disyllabic reduplication to repetition of the entire word
- number (plural) is expressed by partial reduplication
- this is accomplished, with few exceptions, either by simply reduplicating the CV of the stressed syllable once or twice (usually transitive verbs), or by reduplicating the CV of the stressed syllable via infixation of the bisyllabic sequence CVrV, in which C and the two V positions take their values from the onset and nucleus of the reduplicated (stressed) syllable (usually intransitive verbs)
- these two patterns are found
 - (1.) in verbs: *cat/caracat* 'break', *toc/tototoc* 'drink'
 - (2.) in verbal modifiers: *'i/'iri* 'already', *mon/momon* 'slowly'
 - (3.) in inflectional clitics: *na/nana* 'third person realis past/present VIC', *nucun/nucucun* 'third person possessive NIC', (exception: *tara/tatara* 'third person realis future VIC')
 - (4.) in demonstrative pronouns: *cam cwa' / caram cwa'* 'third person feminine'
 - (5.) in suffixation on *xi-* nouns: *winacon/winacocon* 'his/their head'
- reduplication or repetition of the entire verb is a way of expressing the continuous, progressive, and iterative aspects
- total reduplication occurs in derived nouns, to derive names or descriptive terms, e.g. *homa homa* (fat-1s + fat-1s) 'fish species that is very fat', *capija capija* (mouth + mouth) 'talker'
- several examples of iterative derived nouns, where the base is an onomatopoeic term; the base form represents the sound the object makes, e.g. *too too* (noise metal makes when hit + noise metal...) 'boat with a diesel motor'

Clitics and particles

- nominal inflectional clitics (NICs) follow possessed non-xi' nouns to indicate person, number and (3.P.) gender of the possessor → clitics and not suffixes:

- (i) they never bear primary stress and (ii) they fail to undergo V-harmony (or trigger it) with the noun to which they attach
 - follow the free form of most nouns, and function in derived nouns
- verbal inflectional clitics (VICs) → simple clitic
 - as with NICs, VICs fail to undergo V-harmony with the preceding word, and never bear primary stress (fail to undergo word-internal phonological changes which ordinarily happen when morphemes are suffixed to nouns)
 - unlike NICs, they can appear alone in certain types of question responses and discourse circumstances
 - the two parts of the VICs (subject and object agreement) are stressed as a single word (stress on the last syllable) and V-harmony may take the entire VIC in its scope, but is otherwise allowed only within words
 - do not alter the norms for syllable-final stress in words; last syllable of VICs bears secondary stress, while last syllables of verbs bear primary stress; on the other hand, when suffixes occur on nouns, primary stress falls on the last syllable of the suffix
 - these are clitics that behave like separate words outside of compounding processes
 - VIC is a grammatical word but phonologically dependent
- pronoun clitics (a set of proclitics (e.g. *co* 'masc.', *cam* 'fem.'), postverbal inflection, postnominal inflection)
- sentence particles (four classes: temporal, emphatic, rhetorical, dubitative)

IV. Other Questions

Unstressed vowels

- [i], [e], [o], and [Y] in some idiolects glide slightly to [ʻ] in open stressed syllables (esp. those that occur as single words in an utterance or utterance-final), e.g. *ji* [ʻyi] or [[ʻyi] 'palm species'

Word-word combinations (e.g. compounds, incorporation, complex predicates)

- most productive process of deriving subtypes of verbs
 - up to five elements observed in a compound verb form
 - compounds are left-headed and left-branching
 - not productive for nouns
- (see above)

Bipartite stems

- none

Periphrastic morphology

- none; no AUX in this language

Pre- and post-positions

- 'ON has a single preposition, obligatory inflected for person, number and gender of its object